

Performance simulation of combined two-tank latent and thermochemical heat storage systems for high temperature waste heat recovery

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Abstract

Heat storage systems based on 2 tanks thermochemical heat storage are gaining momentum for their utilization in solar power plants or industrial waste heat recovery, since they can efficiently store heat for. However, their performance is generally limited by reactor configuration, design and optimization on the one hand and most importantly on the selection of appropriate thermochemical materials [1]. Metal hydrides, although at the early stage of research and development (in heat storage applications), can offer several advantages over other thermochemical materials (salt hydrates, metal hydroxides, oxide and carbonates) such as high energy storage density and power density. In this study, we present a system that combines latent heat and thermochemical heat storage based on two-tank metal hydrides. The systems consists of two metal hydrides tanks coupled (See Figure 1).

Figure 1. Concept of combined thermal energy system, a) computational model, b) Temperature distribution during the heat charging

During the heat charging the high temperature metal hydride (HTMH) desorbs hydrogen which in turn is stored in the low temperature metal hydride (LTMH). In the meantime, the heat generated from hydrogen absorption in the LTMH tank is stored as latent heat in a phase change material (PCM) jacket surrounding the LTMH tank, to be reused during the heat discharging. For simulations of this heat storage system, a metal hydrides pair based on Mg_2NiH_4 (HTMH)- $LaNi_5$ (LTMH) and Rubitherm RT(Tm) based on commercial phase change materials are selected for discussion. The results of the simulation shows that the performance indicators such as energy density, power density and storage efficiency is a function of the properties of the selected phase change material, more specifically the melting temperature, T_m and the range of transition temperature.

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References

[1] S. Nyallang Nyamsi , M. Lototsky, I. Tolj. Selection of metal hydrides-based thermal energy storage: Energy storage efficiency and density targets. International journal of Hydrogen Energy, 43, 50, 2018, 22568-22583.